

THE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND PROTEIN AMOUNT OF FERGANA, KHOREZM AND TASHKENT TYPES OF EUPHORBIA MILII

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Abstract. This scientific article describes the analysis of elemental analysis of *Euphorbia milii* plant grown in 3 regions of Uzbekistan: Tashkent, Khorezm and Fergana. In the second part of an article the protein analysis is given.

Aim: The purpose is finding necessary elements and amount of protein from vegetative organs of that plant and using this for medicine.

Key words: *Euphorbia*, macro elements, micro elements, heavy metals, protein, spectrum.

Introduction.

To be able to grow, develop, and produce at their best, plants must have specific elements or compounds called plant essential nutrients. A plant that lacks an essential nutrient cannot complete its life cycle—the seed may not germinate; the plant may not be able to develop roots, stems, leaves, or flowers properly; or it may not be able to produce seeds to create new plants. Often the plant itself will die. [1] However, having too much of a nutrient can harm and even kill plants. For example, having too much nitrogen can cause a plant to grow more leaves but less or no fruit. Too much manganese can make the leaves turn yellow and eventually die. And excess boron can kill a plant. [1,4] You can save money and effort—and even your plants—if you know what and how much to give your plants. The plants will be healthier and more productive if you give them what they need—no more and no less. [3] Scientists have identified 16 essential nutrients and grouped them according to the relative amount of each that plants need:

- Primary nutrients, also known as macronutrients, are those usually required in the largest amounts. They are carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, oxygen, phosphorus, and potassium. [6]
- Secondary nutrients are those usually needed in moderate amounts compared to the primary essential nutrients. The secondary nutrients are calcium, magnesium, and sulfur. [6]
- Micro- or trace nutrients are required in tiny amounts compared to primary or secondary nutrients. Micronutrients are boron, chlorine, copper, iron, manganese, molybdenum, and zinc. [5]

The object of work. *Euphorbia milii* or Crown of Thorns is a plant and the main object of the work. This plant is usually the flower that we can keep in our houses.

Crown of Thorns is a deciduous, herbaceous, perennial shrub with bright green leaves and greenish flowers. [6,7] The flowers are enclosed within long-lasting and bright bracts of red or yellow. The plant is loose in form, spiny and irregularly shaped, with thick, black spines and its historic presence in the Middle East led to the belief by some that the stems of this plant had been used in Christ's crown of thorns, hence the common name. In its country of origin (Madagascar) the plant will grow to 5 or 6 feet tall; however, in the United States, it typically grows to 3 feet, or 2 feet when grown as a houseplant. [7]

Crown of Thorns grows best in dry to medium moisture, well-drained soils in full sun. Because it does not like wet, cold soils or temperatures below 35 degrees F. It is an easy to grow indoor plant where it prefers a sunny location in soil-based potting mix. [8] If grown outside in hot summer climates, provide the plant with midday shade and moderate moisture for better flower bloom. You can propagate the plant from tip cuttings; however, because the resulting white latex sap causes a mild poisonous reaction when in contact with skin or eyes, wear gloves when working with this

plant. Sticky, showy, paired-bract flowers on gray stems with long spines identify this plant. [8.9] Cyclical leaf drop is normal, but messy and proceeds the plant's resting season (usually winter). The flowers will bloom throughout the year. The long spines are dangerous to inattentive gardeners, children and pets. The plant is often used as a specimen plant for interiors with high light or as annual outdoor plant. Crown of Thorns prefers bright light, dry soil and low relative humidity. You can propagate the plant from cuttings, but let sap dry before placing the cutting in a growing medium.[10]

Method. 0.1000 g is transferred quantitatively into Teflon autoclaves. 3 ml of purified concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and 2 ml of purified hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) were added to it. The mouth of the autoclave was closed and a microwave disintegrator Berghof (Speed Wave Expert or similar microwave oven) was placed. In this case, a command was given to decompress based on a specific program in the device interface. In this method, the number of specified autoclaves and the temperature and pressure inside them are automatically controlled by the device. Information about the process is controlled by a liquid crystal display. It was carried out under conditions of wet decomposition for 35-45 min under conditions of minimum temperature T (500C) and maximum temperature T (2300C), pressure R [bar] max 40 [bar] inside the autoclaves. The autoclaves were cooled to room temperature and the liquid mixture inside was liquated into a 50 or 100 mL volumetric flask (to the mark). In this, the autoclaves are rinsed 2-3 times and then filled up to the tube line with bidistilled water. The solution is thoroughly mixed and put into the autosampler test tube and placed on the autosampler in a certain numbered place. In the program, the position of each test tube, the mass withdrawn and the dilution factor are entered. (So that the device can calculate the concentration automatically). The mineralized solution is quantitatively analyzed by Perkin Elmer's ISP-MS (Nexion 2000) in inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (or a similar analogue device) in comparison to the standard sample containing the amount of macro and micro elements, heavy metal salts, and rare metals. Analytical results automatically calculate precision and standard deviation (RSD) values by recalculating results based on sample mass and dilution values at the end of the process.

The method consists in determining nitrogen according to Kjeldahl, followed by conversion to protein. The essence of the method consists in the decomposition of the organic matter of the sample by boiling concentrated sulfuric acid with the formation of ammonium salts, the conversion of ammonium into ammonia, its distillation into an acid solution, the quantitative accounting of ammonia by the titrimetric method, and the calculation of the nitrogen content in the test material. From the averaged crushed homogeneous sample of the studied defatted cottonseed meal for analysis, an accurate sample was weighed in a test tube, with an error of no more than 0.1%. The sample was quantitatively transferred to a Kjeldahl flask. Further, the experiments were carried out according to the guidelines [3].

Results processing.

The mass fraction of nitrogen (X) in the test sample as a percentage of its mass during the distillation of ammonia into sulfuric acid was calculated by the formula

$$X = \frac{(V_1 - V_0) \times K \times 0,0014 \times 100}{M}, \text{ где}$$

V_0 – volume of 0.1 mol/l sodium hydroxide solution used for titration of 0.05 mol/l sulfuric acid in the control experiment, ml

V_1 is the volume of 0.1 mol/l sodium hydroxide solution used for titration of sulfuric acid in the test solution, ml;

K - correction to the titer of 0.1 mol / l sodium hydroxide solution;

0.0014 - the amount of nitrogen equivalent to 1 ml of 0.05 mol / l sulfuric acid solution;

M is the weight of the sample, g.[4,6]

The arithmetic mean of the results of five parallel tests was taken as the final test result. The results were calculated to the third decimal place and rounded to the second decimal place.

The mass fraction of nitrogen in terms of the dry matter of the product (X_3), in percent, was calculated by the formula:

$$X_3 = \frac{X_1 \times 100}{100 - W}, \text{ где}$$

X_1 is the mass fraction of nitrogen in the test sample, %;

W is the humidity of the test sample, %.

The mass fraction of protein (Y) in percent was calculated by the formula:

$Y = K H X$, where

K - coefficient for converting nitrogen to protein:

with a moderate (2-15%) lipid content - 6.38;[5]

Results: The results of the laboratory part is given as tables.

Table 1.

The amount of macro elements of Euphorbia milli stem mg/kg			
Elements	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
Na	209.981	1034.875	2340.630
Mg	1657.376	795.474	8434.855
Al	9.778	8.498	123.034
Si	706.637	734.759	2227.479
P	2394.210	5356.630	31832.782
K	7856.018	5552.527	58493.105
Ca	1454.261	1080.172	4001.655
Si	706.637	734.759	2227.479

Table 2.

№	The amount of micro elements of Euphorbia milii stem, mg/kg			
	Elements	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
1	Ge	0.000	0.000	0.001
2	Se	0.026	0.021	0.004
3	Sr	2.444	3.414	15.081
4	Zr	0.006	0.003	0.035
5	Mo	0.036	0.004	0.110
6	Ag	0.001	0.001	0.002

7	Rb	0.098	0.073	1.966
8	In	0.000	0.000	0.000
9	Cs	0.000	0.000	0.001
10	Ba	0.248	0.226	0.633
11	Ta	0.001	0.001	0.001
12	W	0.000	0.001	0.001
13	Re	0.000	0.000	0.000
14	Tl	0.000	0.000	0.000
15	Ti	21.346	5.171	39.889
16	V	0.005	0.022	0.091
17	Sr	2.444	3.414	15.081
18	Mn	0.505	0.385	1.964
19	Co	0.009	0.011	0.056
20	Ni	0.086	0.079	0.639
21	Cu	0.061	0.027	0.468
22	Zn	0.731	0.743	1.792
23	Ga	0.066	0.055	0.142
24	Li	0.031	0.135	1.469
25	Be	0.004	0.003	0.009
26	B	4.998	4.194	2.223
27	Sn	0.067	0.001	0.091
28	Cr	0.273	0.460	1.518
29	Nb	0.000	0.000	0.002
30	Fe	80.256	64.005	255.493

Table 3.

The amount of heavy metals of Euphorbia milli stem mg/kg			
Metalls	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
As	0.008	0.010	0.050
Cd	0.001	0.001	0.003
Sb	0.001	0.000	0.015
Hg	0.005	0.001	0.002
Pb	0.017	0.019	0.009
Bi	0.001	0.000	0.000
U	0.001	0.001	0.005

Table 4.

The amount of macro elements of <i>Euphorbia milli</i> leaves mg/kg			
Elements	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
Na	248.552	1121.578	251.250
Mg	3252.808	795.474	11132.163
Al	22.521	8.498	43.859
Si	2017.423	1924.479	2710.636
P	11847.291	14937.832	12220.227
K	18575.198	42367.097	26178.584
Ca	3032.463	3785.265	41715.064
S	2840.987	3280.907	3668.191

Table 5.

№	The amount of micro elements of <i>Euphorbia milii</i> leaves, mg/kg			
	Elements	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
1	Ge	0.000	0.000	0.001
2	As	0.333	0.124	0.110
3	Se	0.081	0.043	0.059
4	Sn	0.065	0.010	0.076
5	Sr	1.944	9.105	24.984
6	Zr	0.028	0.015	0.053
7	Nb	0.000	0.001	0.001
8	Mo	0.066	0.089	0.010
9	Ag	0.001	0.001	0.001
10	Rb	0.198	0.511	0.767
11	In	0.000	0.000	0.000
12	Cs	0.000	0.000	0.001
13	Ba	0.474	0.360	0.849
14	Ta	0.001	0.001	0.001

15	W	0.004	0.004	0.000
16	Re	0.003	0.000	0.001
17	B	36.458	5.665	14.670
18	Tl	0.001	0.000	0.000
19	Be	0.008	0.000	0.011
20	Li	2.158	0.931	2.116
21	Ti	41.639	1956.015	91.895
22	V	0.024	0.067	0.069
23	Ga	0.119	0.084	0.185
24	Mn	2.583	2.412	3.901
25	Co	0.037	0.042	0.081
26	Ni	0.178	0.392	0.571
27	Cu	0.149	1.165	0.356
28	Zn	1.171	4.145	2.245
29	Ga	0.119	0.084	0.185
30	Fe	178.369	227.276	473.459

Table 7.

The amount of heavy metals of Euphorbia milli leaves mg/kg			
Metalls	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
As	0.333	0.124	0.110
Cd	0.001	0.002	0.005
Sb	0.003	0.002	0.003
Hg	0.002	0.002	0.002
Pb	0.018	0.026	0.006
Bi	0.001	0.000	0.001
U	0.001	0.002	0.011

Table 8.

The amount of macro elements of Euphorbia milli root mg/kg			
Elements	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
Na	1583.098	22740.233	4422.356
Mg	1898.458	4767.549	2270.677
Al	661.126	464.225	141.572
Si	2613.168	2964.889	395.529
P	3355.262	18073.016	3648.550
K	10806.038	38186.204	10673.753
Ca	1507.026	2928.694	9602.228
Si	2613.168	2964.889	395.529
S	1963.321	3434.225	766.022

Table 9.

№	The amount of micro elements of Euphorbia milii root, mg/kg			
	Elements	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
1	Ge	0.001	0.001	0.012
2	Ga	0.122	0.116	0.356
3	Se	0.014	0.063	0.506
4	Sn	0.120	0.050	1.624
5	Sr	2.240	10.292	44.369
6	Zr	0.016	0.025	0.104
7	Nb	0.002	0.002	0.013
8	Mo	0.115	0.133	3.638
9	Ag	0.014	0.001	0.015
10	Rb	0.194	0.767	8.743
11	In	0.000	0.000	0.000
12	Cs	0.002	0.000	0.034
13	Ba	0.423	0.459	9.829

14	Ta	0.001	0.001	0.002
15	W	0.001	0.001	0.085
16	Re	0.000	0.000	0.002
17	B	7.463	2.606	97.109
18	Tl	0.001	0.000	0.014
19	Be	0.007	0.007	0.173
20	Li	0.619	1.749	1.994
21	Ti	1.847	15.256	369.110
22	V	0.329	0.456	1.074
23	Tl	0.001	0.000	0.014
24	Mn	0.335	3.082	15.495
25	Co	0.045	0.066	0.306
26	Ni	0.206	0.279	4.436
27	Cu	0.508	0.428	3.318
28	Zn	1.860	1.117	10.667
29	Fe	219.203	276.947	705.514
30	Cr	0.496	0.966	6.110

Table 10.

The amount of heavy metals of Euphorbia milli root mg/kg			
Metalls	Tashkent	Khorezm	Fergana
As	0.057	0.429	0.960
Cd	0.003	0.003	0.112
Sb	0.002	0.003	0.065
Hg	0.004	0.005	0.737
Pb	0.012	0.021	3.976
Bi	0.001	0.001	0.009
U	0.003	0.009	0.165

Based on the table given below, we can say that among the leaves of the plants of the 3 regions, the protein content of the Euphorbia miliii plant grown in Fergana region is the highest. The lowest amount of protein was determined in the leaves of the Euphorbia miliii plant grown in Khorezm region, i.e. in the desert zone.

Table 1.

Name	Fergana	Tashkent	Khorezm
Leaf (Protein%)	16.670	11.742	6.103

Table 2 shows the amount of protein in the stem of Euphorbia Miliiii growing in 3 different zones. According to this, it was determined that the most amount of protein is in the stem of the plant grown in Fergana region, and the least amount of protein is in the stem of the plant grown in Tashkent region.

Table 2.

Name	Fergana	Tashkent	Khorezm
Stem (Protein%)	14.803	6.308	6.951

Table 3 shows how much protein is present in the root parts of Euphorbia Miliiii plants grown in 3 regions. According to the results, the most amount of protein was collected in the root of the plant grown in Fergana region, and the least amount of protein was found in the root of the plant grown in Khorezm region.

Table 3.

Name	Fergana	Tashkent	Khorezm
Root (Protein%)	9.612	6.858	4.366

Table 4 below summarizes the findings from the plant samples. According to the results, the Euphorbia Miliiii plant grown in Fergana region accumulates protein mainly in the leaf and stem, but the amount of protein is more in the leaf than in the stem. The Euphorbia Miliiii plant grown in Tashkent region accumulates a large amount of protein mainly in its leaves, while the amount of protein in the stem and root is very low. The Euphorbia Miliiii plant grown in Tashkent region accumulates a large amount of protein mainly in its leaves, while the amount of protein in the stem and root is very low.

Table 4.

Types	Samples	Protein(%)
Fergana region	leaf	16.670
	stem	14.803
	root	9.612
Tashkent	leaf	11.742
	stem	6.308
	root	6.858
Khorazm region	leaf	6.103
	stem	6.951
	root	4.366

Conclusion.

As a conclusion, it can be said that macro, micro and heavy metals were detected in all vegetative organs of Euphorbia miliiii grown in 3 regions of Uzbekistan: Tashkent, Khorezm and

Fergana. This leads to the conclusion that this plant can be a source for the production of biologically active supplements in folk medicine. If we do a deeper analysis, it was found that the stems of 3 types of *Euphorbia miliii* mainly contain macro elements, and very small amounts of micro and ultra-micro elements were found.

The results of the analysis showed that the stems and leaves of the *Euphorbia miliii* plant grown in Fergana region contain a large amount of macro and micro elements. Macro elements were also detected in the plants collected from Tashkent and Khorezm regions, but the amount of micro elements in their leaves is much less. The leaf richest in microelements is the leaf of *Euphorbia miliii* grown in Fergana region.

When the roots of the plants taken from 3 regions were analyzed, significant differences were found, that is, the roots of the *Euphorbia miliii* plant from the Khorezm region contained the most macro elements. The amount of macroelements in the roots of *Euphorbia miliii* grown in Fergana and Tashkent is low and almost the same. If we take a deeper look, we find out that the root of *Euphorbia miliii* grown in Khorezm region contains a lot of some microelements, for example, Ti, Fe and Sr elements. But compared to other elements, the amount of micro and ultra-micro elements in the roots of plants from all 3 regions is low and equal. In summary, among the plants grown in the 3 selected regions: Fergana, Tashkent and Khorezm, *Euphorbia Miliii*, grown in the mountainous region of Fergana region, contains the largest amount of protein. Unfortunately, the *Euphorbia Miliii* plant grown in the desert zone, i.e. in the Khorezm region, is not rich in protein. We have chosen the species grown in Fergana region for future research, namely, to apply *Euphorbia Miliii* to the production of immune-enhancing drugs. Based on all the results, we believe that it is correct to choose 2 species to add to the composition of protein-preserving drugs and biologically active supplements: species grown in Fergana and Tashkent region. The type growing in the Khorezm region can continue to beautify homes as a beautiful ornamental flower.

In summary, *Euphorbia miliii* plants grown in 3 regions of Uzbekistan with different climates (desert, mountain and mixed climate) accumulate macro, micro and heavy metals mainly in the stems and leaves. . Taking this into account, in the next parts of the scientific work, it was aimed to use the above-ground vegetative organs of plants to prepare a biologically active supplement. Taking into account the large number of types of biogenic elements in its composition, it is possible to use the biologically active supplement prepared from the *Euphorbia miliii* plant as a means of increasing immunity.

Ethical statement.

As an author of this article I can say that this is an original article, no copy from another sources, done by ourselves.

Literatures:

1. Ashraf, R.A. Sarfraz, F. Anwar, S.A. Shahid, K.M. Alkharfy. **Chemical composition and biological activities of leaves of *Ziziphus mauritiana* L. native to Pakistan.** Pak. J. Bot., 47 (1) (2015), pp. 367-376
2. S. Bani, A. Kaul, B. Khan, V.K. Gupta, N.K. Satti, K.A. Suri, *et al.* Anti-arthritis activity of a biopolymeric fraction from *Euphorbia tirucalli* J. Ethnopharmacol., 110 (1) (2007), pp. 92-98
3. A.D. Becke Density thermochemistry. I. The role of exact exchange J. Chem., 98 (7) (1980), pp. 5648-5660
4. H.J. Berendsen, Postma Jv, W.F. van Gunsteren, A. DiNola, J. Haak. Molecular dynamics with coupling to an external bath. J. Chem. Phys., 81 (8) (1984), pp. 3684-3690

5. Freddie Bray, Jacques Ferlay, Isabelle Soerjomataram, Rebecca Siegel, Lindsey A. Torre, Ahmedi Jemal Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries *CA Cancer J. Clin.*, 68 (6) (2018), pp. 394-424
6. M. Bruncko, T.K. Oost, B.A. Belli, H. Ding, M.K. Joseph, A. Kunzer, *et al.* Studies leading to potent, dual inhibitors of Bcl-2 and Bcl-xL. *Med. Chem.*, 50 (4) (2007), pp. 641-662
7. S. Chaman, F.Z. Khan, R. Khokhar, H. Maab, S. Qamar, S. Zahid, *et al.* Cytotoxic and antiviral potentials of *Euphorbia milii* var. *plendens* leaf against Peste des petits ruminant virus *Trop. J. Pharm. Res.*, 18 (7) (2019), pp. 1507-1511
8. S. Charoensiddhi, P. Anprung Bioactive compounds and volatile compounds of Thai bael fruit (*Aegle marmelos* (L.) Correa) as a valuable source for functional food ingredients *Int. Food Res. J.*, 15 (3) (2008), pp. 287-295
9. T.A. Chohan, H. Qian, Y. Pan, J.-Z. Chen Cyclin-dependent kinase-2 as a target for cancer therapy: progress in the development of CDK2 inhibitors as anti-cancer agents *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 22 (2) (2015), pp. 237-263
10. Clark, R.D. Cramer III, N. Van Opdenbosch Validation of the general purpose Tripos 5.2 force field *J. Comput. Chem.*, 10 (8) (1989), pp. 982-1012